

1 Title: How exposure to a neonicotinoid pesticide affects innate and learned close-range foraging
2 behaviour of a classical biological control agent

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13

14 **Abstract**

15 While foraging in agricultural habitats, natural enemies, such as egg parasitoids, may encounter
16 insecticide residues, which, if not lethal, can alter host location behaviour and learning capacity.

17 Such interference can reduce the potential of biological control agents, especially exotic species
18 which are released in small numbers in a new environment and first need to establish and build
19 up their populations. Several studies have investigated the lethal effects of pesticides on

20 parasitoids, but less information is available about non-lethal consequences, and no information
21 is available on the potential effect on associative learning in egg parasitoids. The egg parasitoid

22 *Trissolcus japonicus* (Ashmed) (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae) is a biological control agent of the

23 invasive brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae). We

24 hypothesised that a low concentration (causing 20% parasitoid mortality) of a commonly used
25 neonicotinoid insecticide (acetamiprid) alters the behaviour and learning capacity of *T. japonicus*
26 to exploit the chemical traces left by reproductive females of either the main host, *H. halys*, or of
27 an alternative host, *Arma custos* (F.) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae). In open arena bioassays,
28 parasitoid females responded positively to traces left by both stink bug species. Following
29 oviposition experience and encounter with host traces (associative learning), *T. japonicus*
30 reduced foraging time. Parasitoids previously exposed to neonicotinoid showed changes in
31 foraging behaviour, with increased residence time spent in the host-contaminated area and
32 altered kinetics of the walking behaviour. Neonicotinoid exposition did not affect the learning
33 ability of parasitoid females 1 h after oviposition experience but prolonged the memory
34 retention. The insecticide effects on female parasitoid behaviour may affect its reproductive
35 ability and this should be considered when attempting its establishment in the introduction areas.

36

37 **Keywords:** associative learning, biological invasion, brown marmorated stink bug, egg
38 parasitoid, *Halyomorpha halys*, *Trissolcus japonicus*

39

40 **1. Introduction**

41 In classical biological control programs, the establishment of an exotic natural enemy after
42 release is a critical factor for success ([Hoelmer and Kirk, 2005](#); [Heimpel and Asplen, 2011](#);
43 [Segoli et al., 2023](#)). In addition to the natural enemy life history traits, the environmental context
44 including plant-related factors and crop management can facilitate or hinder its establishment
45 ([Rusch et al., 2010](#); [Pajač Živković et al., 2021](#)). Surprisingly, the importance of understanding
46 the ability of biological control agents to cope with agricultural practices is recognised but often
47 overlooked ([Letourneau and Bothwell, 2008](#); [Jonsson et al., 2012](#); [Renou and Anton, 2020](#);

48 [Monticelli et al., 2021](#)). Invasive pests that become established in a new area can disrupt
49 integrated pest management programmes and lead to overuse of pesticides ([Venette and Morey,](#)
50 [2019](#)). Among natural enemies, parasitoids are particularly vulnerable to pesticides ([Desneux et](#)
51 [al., 2007](#); [Teder and Knapp, 2019](#)). They can be contaminated directly during field spraying and
52 by contact with dry residues on plant tissues, or indirectly when developing in contaminated
53 hosts ([Penca and Hodges, 2017](#); [Sánchez-Bayo, 2021](#)). Additional contamination can occur
54 through consumption of nectar and pollen from plants treated with systemic insecticides, such as
55 neonicotinoids ([Stapel et al., 2000](#); [Tappert et al., 2017](#); [Calvo-Agudo et al., 2019](#)).
56 Several studies have highlighted the lethal effects of pesticides on parasitoids ([Biondi et al.,](#)
57 [2013](#); [Ohta and Takeda, 2015](#); [Pinheiro et al., 2020](#); [Ribeiro et al., 2021](#)). Non-lethal effects
58 caused by low pesticide concentrations can also be important and may consist of behavioural and
59 physiological changes on individuals that survive exposure ([Desneux et al., 2007](#); [Teder and](#)
60 [Knapp, 2019](#); [Rakes et al., 2021](#); [Giunti et al., 2022](#); [Schöfer et al., 2023](#)). Interference with host
61 location, inhibition of population establishment, progeny development, decreased female
62 reproduction, and altered sex ratio have been documented ([Delpuech et al., 2012](#); [Moscardini et](#)
63 [al., 2014](#); [Tappert et al., 2017](#); [Pazini et al., 2019](#); [Lisi et al., 2023](#)). Infochemical detection and
64 decoding by parasitoids are crucial for efficient host location ([Vet and Dicke, 1992](#)), and
65 neurotoxic insecticides can alter their ability to recognise, learn, and memorise host associated
66 chemosensory molecules ([Stapel et al., 2000](#); [Tappert et al., 2017](#); [Schöfer et al., 2023](#); [Shi et al.,](#)
67 [2024](#)). Surprisingly, the effects of pesticides on learning behaviour and memory retention have
68 rarely been studied in parasitoids ([Rafalimanana et al., 2002](#); [Desneux et al., 2004](#)), with no
69 information available for hymenopteran egg parasitoids. On the other hand, negative effects have
70 been reported in studies focusing on hymenopteran pollinators ([Desneux et al., 2007](#); [Stanley and](#)
71 [Preetha, 2016](#); [Tison et al., 2017](#); [Muth and Leonard, 2019](#)), and may provide a fundamental

72 background for parasitic wasps. It is therefore advisable to screen pesticides used against an
73 invasive pest for side effects on parasitoid foraging behaviour ([Abram et al., 2020](#)). These can
74 hinder the success as biological control agent by reducing the likelihood of establishment of the
75 small initial population or its parasitisation efficacy. For locating unapparent eggs at short
76 distance, egg parasitoids often rely on detectable cues, such as chemical traces left by
77 physogastric host females ([Colazza et al., 2014](#); [Hilker and Fatouros, 2015](#); [Greenberg et al.,
78 2023](#)). The innate response of the parasitoid to host-associated cues may adjust during foraging,
79 for example in response to repeated encounters with the host and successful oviposition events,
80 leading to improved reproductive success ([Turlings et al., 1993](#); [Kruidhof et al., 2012](#); [Kruidhof
81 et al., 2019](#); [Gonthier et al., 2023](#)). It is also expected that the parasitoid can distinguish between
82 the traces left by different host species, thus exhibiting a different searching behaviour depending
83 on the host quality ([Vet and Groenewold, 1990](#); [Heimpel et al., 1996](#)).

84 The family of Scelionidae includes important egg parasitoids that have been widely introduced
85 into new areas for biological control of stink bug pests ([Orr, 1988](#); [Conti et al., 2021](#)). *Trissolcus*
86 *japonicus* (Ashmead) (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae) is the main egg parasitoid of the polyphagous
87 pest *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in their native range in Asia ([Yang et
88 al., 2009](#); [Zhang et al., 2017](#); [Leskey and Nielsen, 2018](#)). The parasitoid has been recently
89 introduced as a classical biological control agent in Italian natural and agricultural areas, highly
90 infested by *H. halys*, resulting in variable levels of establishment and parasitisation ([Zapponi et
91 al., 2021](#)). In addition, *T. japonicus* has the capacity to develop in some native stink bugs co-
92 occurring with *H. halys*, such as *Arma custos* (F.) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) ([Haye et al., 2020](#);
93 [Sabbatini-Peverieri et al., 2021](#); [Haye et al., 2023](#)). This is a predatory stink bug and can be
94 considered a low quality host for *T. japonicus*, because of the small size of the eggs and the
95 altered physiology and behaviour of the parasitoid adult progeny ([Chierici et al., 2023](#)).

96 Using the study system consisting of *T. japonicus*, *H. halys*, and *A. custos*, we primarily aimed at
97 evaluating whether a low concentration of a neonicotinoid insecticide (acetamiprid) affects the
98 close-range foraging behaviour of the parasitoid.
99 More specifically, using open and closed arena bioassays, we recorded the searching behaviour
100 of *T. japonicus* towards traces of host females in their pre-ovipositional phase, which are used by
101 the parasitoid as a proxy for the egg presence ([Boyle et al., 2020b](#)). In Experiment 1, we
102 hypothesised that: i) *T. japonicus* exploits chemical cues of the two stink bug species and may
103 exhibit preferences for the main host *H. halys* in comparison to the alternative host, *A. custos*; ii)
104 after conditioning (encounter with host traces and oviposition success), *T. japonicus* may modify
105 the searching behaviour differently for the two hosts; iii) exposition to low neonicotinoid
106 concentration can modify the innate and conditioned foraging behaviour of *T. japonicus*, with
107 possible differences among the stink bug traces. In Experiment 2, we focussed on the main host
108 *H. halys* and aimed at confirming that the mechanism behind parasitoid conditioning can be
109 ascribed to associative learning ([Papaj and Prokopy, 1989](#); [Vet et al., 1990](#); [Matsumoto et al.,](#)
110 [2012](#)), and we also evaluated the effect of the neonicotinoid on the parasitoid memory retention.
111 In Experiment 3, we mainly hypothesised that neonicotinoid exposition alters the innate
112 locomotory activity (kinetic) of *T. japonicus* females.

113

114 **2. Materials and methods**

115 *2.1. Stink bugs*

116 Colonies of *H. halys* and *A. custos* were established from adults collected every year since 2021
117 in natural and agricultural ecosystems located in north and central Italy. Stink bugs were
118 maintained in several mesh cages (Kweekkooi, 40 × 40 × 60 cm, Vermandel, Hulst, The
119 Netherlands), under controlled climatic chamber (25 ± 1 °C, 60 ± 5% relative humidity, 16/8 h

120 light/dark) ([Chierici et al., 2023](#)). Approximately, 60 males and females of each species were
121 reared in each cage, with a total number of adults in the laboratory ranging approximately from
122 300 to 700 (*H. halys*) or 100 to 200 (*A. custos*). *Halyomorpha halys* were fed with carrots,
123 sunflower seeds, and fruits (apples, pears, hazelnuts, kiwis). *Arma custos* were fed with pupae of
124 *Tenebrio molitor* L. (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). Food was replaced three times per week. Water
125 was provided with an upside-down glass jar sealed with cotton on a Petri dish (9 cm diam.).
126 Oviposition substrate consisted in towel papers placed on the bottom of the cage. Stink bug eggs
127 were daily collected, and some were frozen at -20 °C and used for parasitoid rearing (*H. halys*)
128 or for oviposition bioassays (*H. halys* and *A. custos*). Stink bug females in pre-ovipositional
129 phase (physogastric abdomen) were used for bioassays ([Rondoni et al., 2022](#)). At this stage,
130 females release on the substrate chemical traces which may represent kairomones for foraging
131 egg parasitoids ([Peri et al., 2006](#); [Boyle et al., 2020b](#); [Bertoldi et al., 2021](#)).

132

133 2.2. Parasitoids

134 Adult *T. japonicus* were provided by CREA (courtesy of P.F. Roversi and G. Sabbatini-Peverieri,
135 details of the parasitoid strain in [Chierici et al., 2023](#)) and were reared in Falcon tubes (50 mL,
136 Corning, Italy) sealed on one side with a fine plastic mesh. The colony was maintained in a
137 climatic chamber at 25 ± 1 °C, $60 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, and 16/8h light/dark ([Chierici et al.,](#)
138 [2023](#)). Pure honey was provided on a piece (2×2 cm) of Parafilm® (Bemis, USA) three times a
139 week. Males and females were kept together to allow mating. For colony maintenance, a mated
140 *T. japonicus* female was isolated in a Falcon tube and allowed to parasitise one *H. halys* egg
141 mass within a 24 h period. Newly emerged parasitoid females were allowed to mate prior to be
142 randomly assigned to the different treatments. Insects of about 8 days were selected for
143 experiments because previous investigations on the same *T. japonicus* colony revealed a higher

144 number of mature eggs at 8 days onward ([Chierici et al., 2023](#)). Following exposure to a low
145 concentration of a neonicotinoid insecticide or acetone solution (control) (see section 2.3 for
146 details), parasitoids were either tested as naïve, i.e., a female without foraging and oviposition
147 experience, or conditioned, i.e., a female that had encountered the traces left by a physogastric
148 stink bug female of the host species and was rewarded with an oviposition experience ([Bertoldi
149 et al., 2021](#), see section 2.4 for details).

150

151 *2.3. Determination of a neonicotinoid concentration inducing low parasitoid mortality*

152 The exposure of *T. japonicus* to field residues of insecticide was carried out by allowing the
153 insect to walk on a surface (inner area of a 2 ml glass tube, 15.6 cm²) contaminated with dry
154 residues of a commercial neonicotinoid (Epik SL, containing 4.7% acetamiprid, Sipcam, Italy).
155 The contamination of the tube was conducted according to residual test bioassays ([Li et al.,
156 2024](#)) and the IRAC Susceptibility Test Method, No 30, v. 1.2 (<https://irac-online.org/methods/>),
157 which describes the procedure for the conversion of the dosage applied in open field (1.6 L/ha)
158 to the glass tube (0.016 µl/cm², for a total of 0.24 µl insecticide per tube). The field dosage
159 adopted is an average of the recommended field doses reported in the commercial product label
160 for important *H. halys* horticultural tree hosts (nuts, pome and stone fruits). The 0.24 µl of
161 insecticide was diluted in 600 µl total solution per glass tube, using acetone as solvent ([Li et al.,
162 2019](#)). Serial dilutions of 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.13, 1.56, 0.78, 0.39, 0.20, and 0.10 % were
163 prepared from 100 % of the insecticide field dose ([Li et al., 2019](#)). Pure acetone was used as
164 control. The tubes filled with each dilution solution were tightly inserted in a plastic rack,
165 vertically affixed to an electronic motor (6 V) placed under a fume hood at room temperature
166 (25° C). A gently automatic rotation (2 rounds per min) of the rack was provided during solvent
167 evaporation, allowing a uniform deposition of the insecticide on the internal side of the glass

168 vials. To avoid leakage of the solution, the tubes were initially placed with a small degree of
169 inclination (+10 °), that was manually decreased to 0° until the acetone completely evaporated.
170 Fine-mesh nets, to be subsequently used to close the glass tubes, were dipped in the
171 corresponding insecticide concentrations or acetone only (for control), and dried under the fume
172 hood.

173 Groups of five mated parasitoid females were then transferred to the treated tubes. In total, 30
174 parasitoids were evaluated per each dilution. Three drops of pure honey were provided upon a
175 Parafilm® plastic strip (2 × 10 mm) as nourishment. After 12 h of continuous exposition,
176 parasitoids were transferred to clean tubes (food provided), and mortality was assessed after
177 additional 24 h ([Stanley and Preetha, 2016](#)). Only parasitoids that did not move when touched
178 with a fine paintbrush were considered dead. Mortality data were used to estimate the
179 neonicotinoid concentration causing 20% of parasitoid mortality, which was adopted for
180 subsequent behavioural bioassays.

181

182 *2.4. Preparation of Trissolcus japonicus for bioassays and conditioning procedure*

183 Conditioned parasitoid females were obtained as follows: a female of either *H. halys* or *A.*
184 *custos* in their pre-ovipositional phase was introduced in the middle of a filter paper sheath (20 ×
185 20 cm, 80 g/m², 0.185 mm thickness, Filter-lab, Barcelona, Spain). The stink bug was
186 immediately caged using the bottom of a Petri dish (5 cm diam., 1 cm height) placed upside-
187 down. This procedure allowed the stink bug to freely walk for 30 min on the restrained portion of
188 the filter paper and to contaminate it with chemical traces ([Bertoldi et al., 2021](#); [Peri et al., 2021](#)).
189 Stink bugs were continuously monitored to ensure that they spent most of their time walking on
190 the filter paper and not on the Petri dish. Filter papers contaminated with stink bug faeces were
191 discarded ([Bertoldi et al., 2021](#)). After removal of the stink bug, a cluster of 5-6 eggs of the same

192 stink bug species was positioned at the centre of the paper. A naïve *T. japonicus* female was then
193 released in the arena to allow oviposition experience. If at least one oviposition event occurred
194 within 30 min, the female was isolated in a 2 ml tube for 1 h before being tested as a conditioned
195 parasitoid. Subsamples (~120) of the parasitised egg mass clusters were isolated in 2 ml tubes
196 until the emergence of the parasitoids, confirming that oviposition had occurred.

197

198 2.5. Arena bioassays

199 Experiments 1 and 2 were conducted in open arena. A 5 cm diameter area was delineated at the
200 centre of a filter paper (20 × 20 cm) using a fine pencil and exposed to 30 min walking of a *H.*
201 *halys* or *A. custos* female in pre-ovipositional phase, as described above and in [Bertoldi et al.](#)
202 [\(2021\)](#). For the bioassays, a *T. japonicus* female was released in the middle of the contaminated
203 area and the behaviour was visually recorded by two operators using JWatcher 1.0 ([Blumstein,](#)
204 [2006](#)). The bioassay stopped when the wasp abandoned the arena (either walking or flying), or
205 after 10 min ([Bertoldi et al., 2021](#)). The few individuals that flew away immediately after
206 introduction (< 1 s) were considered not motivated to forage and were discarded from the
207 analysis. Similarly, a few additional individuals always remained in the internal contaminated
208 area of the arena throughout the 10 min period. This was not correlated with a particular
209 treatment and was interpreted as a symptom of very low mobility of wasps. Each arena was only
210 used once and, for each treatment, 56 to 66 parasitoids were tested in Experiments 1 and 2.
211 The total time spent by the female in the contaminated area of the arena (residence time) and the
212 number of times the parasitoid entered in the contaminated area (number of visits) were
213 analysed. For convention, high residence time and number of visits are indication of an intensive
214 searching behaviour of the parasitoid and interest for the area under exploration, typically

215 associated with the presence of host-associated kairomones ([Salerno et al., 2002](#); [Bertoldi et al.,](#)
216 [2021](#)).

217 Experiment 3 was conducted in a closed arena consisting of a Munger cell carved in a
218 polycarbonate plate (90 × 90 × 8 mm thick; internal hole diameter: 60 mm) and sandwiched
219 between two glass plates (each plate: 90 × 90 × 5 mm thick). Each glass plate was exposed to 30
220 min walking of a physogastric *H. halys* female, as described above. Parasitoid females were
221 singly introduced into the closed arena and allowed to move freely for 5 min. Insect behaviour
222 was recorded with a monochrome Sony CCD video camera fitted with a 12.5–75 mm/F 1.8 zoom
223 lens. The camera lens was covered with an infrared pass filter to remove visible wavelengths.
224 Video signals from the camera were digitized by a video frame grabber and processed by XBug,
225 a video tracking and motion analysis system (21 frames/sec) ([Colazza et al., 1999](#)). After each
226 bioassay, the glass plates were deterged with a laboratory soap (2% solution of Cleanilab LM1;
227 Kartell Spa, Noviglio, Italy), and rinsed with water and acetone. The plastic parts were cleaned
228 with laboratory soap and rinsed with tap water. To avoid recording the insect when it was
229 walking in the proximity of the lateral side of the Munger cell, only an internal area of 50 mm
230 diameter was eventually analysed. For each treatment, the behaviour of 15 parasitoids was
231 recorded.

232 For closed arena bioassays, insect response was measured in terms of linear speed (mm/s),
233 tortuosity index (defined as $1 - mp/tl$, where mp is the projection of the track in the general
234 straight line of the plan, and tl is the total length of the track), and activity index (the proportion
235 of time spent moving) (details of index calculations in [Salerno et al., 2002](#); [Borges et al., 2003](#);
236 [Laumann et al., 2007](#)). Tortuosity and activity indexes vary from zero to one.

237

238 2.6. *Experiment 1. Combined effect of neonicotinoid exposition, parasitoid conditioning, and*
239 *host species traces on Trissolcus japonicus foraging behaviour (open arena bioassays)*

240 In a first set of comparisons, we evaluated, in a filter paper open arena, the combined effect of
241 insecticide exposition (control or neonicotinoid), parasitoid conditioning (naïve or conditioned),
242 and host species traces (*H. halys* or *A. custos*) on the behaviour of *T. japonicus* females.

243 The treatments consisted of:

244 1a) control (acetone-exposed) naïve parasitoids tested on traces of *H. halys*;

245 1b) neonicotinoid-exposed naïve parasitoids tested on traces of *H. halys*;

246 1c) control parasitoids conditioned on *H. halys* eggs and traces, and tested on traces of *H. halys* 1
247 h after conditioning;

248 1d) neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids conditioned on *H. halys* eggs and traces, and tested on
249 traces of *H. halys* 1 h after conditioning;

250 1e) control naïve parasitoids tested on traces of *A. custos*;

251 1f) neonicotinoid-exposed naïve parasitoids tested on traces of *A. custos*;

252 1g) control parasitoids conditioned on *A. custos* eggs and traces, and tested on traces of *A. custos*
253 1 h after conditioning;

254 1h) neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids conditioned on *A. custos* eggs and traces, and tested on
255 traces of *A. custos* 1 h after conditioning.

256 Additionally, to confirm that *T. japonicus* does respond to stink bug traces, we also recorded the
257 response of control (treatment 1i) or neonicotinoid-exposed (treatment 1j) naïve parasitoids
258 towards a clean filter paper, i.e., not contaminated by stink bug traces ([Malek et al., 2021](#)),
259

260 2.7. *Experiment 2. Confirmation of Trissolcus japonicus associative learning behaviour on H.*
261 *halys and evaluation of memory retention (open arena bioassays)*

262 To verify the occurrence of associative learning mechanism after parasitoid conditioning, the
263 following treatments were conducted:
264 2a-b) control parasitoids, tested 24 and 72 h after conditioning, and compared to treatment 1c
265 (parasitoids tested 1 h after conditioning);
266 2c-d) neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids, tested 24 and 72 h after conditioning, and compared to
267 treatment 1d (parasitoids tested 1 h after conditioning).
268 Because results of Experiment 1 eventually suggested that conditioning was not influenced by
269 the host species, we only focussed on *H. halys* host. Moreover, because oviposition *per se* can
270 increase or decrease a female's subsequent motivation to oviposit ([Wang et al., 2023](#)), we tested
271 the effect of oviposition *per se* without the presence of stink bug traces (*H. halys* only). In
272 details, naïve parasitoids were transferred to a 2 ml clean glass tube with a portion of *H. halys*
273 egg mass consisting of a cluster of 5-6 eggs. Parasitoids were allowed to oviposit for 30 min, and
274 following successful oviposition, they were isolated for 1 h and tested in an open arena
275 contaminated with *H. halys* traces (treatment 2e). This treatment was conducted using parasitoids
276 not exposed to neonicotinoid and was compared to treatment 1c.

277

278 *2.8. Experiment 3. Influence of the combined effect of neonicotinoid exposition and presence of*
279 *H. halys traces on the locomotory activity (kinetic) of naïve T. japonicus (closed arena*
280 *bioassays)*

281 To better understand how insecticide exposition affects the locomotion of naïve *T. japonicus*
282 females, additional bioassays were performed by video recording and analysing the parasitoid
283 behaviour in a closed arena. Treatments consisted of:
284 3a-b) control and neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids tested on a clean arena (no stink bug traces,
285 as in treatments 1i-j);

286 3c-d) control and neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoid females tested in presence of *H. halys* traces
287 (as in treatments 1a-b).

288

289 2.9. Statistical analysis

290 Parasitoid mortality (Section 2.3) was analysed by means of four-parameters log-logistic dose-
291 response model, with lower limit fixed at 0 and upper limit at 1 (package "drc" in R, [Ritz et al.,](#)
292 [2016](#)). The concentration causing 20% of parasitoid mortality was estimated from the model and
293 corresponded to $0.90 \% \pm 0.17$ (SE) of the field dosage (100 %) (Table S1).

294 For closed arena bioassays (Experiment 3), the walking parameters were calculated for each
295 insect by averaging the values of the different segments of the tracking path. Data were box-cox
296 transformed (residence time in Experiments 1 and 2; linear speed in Experiment 3) or arcsine
297 transformed (tortuosity and activity in Experiment 3) and analysed by means of linear model (for
298 data on residence time, linear speed, tortuosity, and activity) or generalised linear model (quasi-
299 Poisson distribution, for number of visits in Experiments 1 and 2) ([Bertoldi et al., 2021](#)). To
300 select the best-fit model, hierarchical model selection based on Likelihood Ratio Test was
301 conducted in R ([R Core Team, 2023](#)).

302

303 3. Results

304 3.1. Experiment 1. Combined effect of neonicotinoid exposition, parasitoid conditioning, and 305 host species traces on *Trissolcus japonicus* foraging behaviour (open arena bioassays)

306 The best-fit model for parasitoid residence time retained the main effects of insecticide
307 exposition, parasitoid conditioning, and host species, without interaction effects (LM, $F_{(3,486)} =$
308 62.44 , $P < 0.0001$, Figure 1, Table S2). For the number of visits in the contaminated area of the
309 arena, the best-fit model retained the main effects of conditioning and host species (quasi-

310 Poisson GLM, $X^2 = 75.47$, $P < 0.0001$, Figure 1, Table S3). Regardless of parasitoid conditioning
311 and host species traces, parasitoid females exposed to neonicotinoid exhibited higher residence
312 time compared to parasitoids in the control group (LM, $P = 0.006$, Table S4). Conditioned
313 females exhibited lower residence time and visits in the experimental arena than naïve females
314 (residence time: $P < 0.0001$, Table S4; visits: $P = 0.0004$, Table S5). Female parasitoids spent
315 more time and visited more frequently the area contaminated with *H. halys* traces compared to *A.*
316 *custos* traces (residence time: $P = 0.0008$; visits: $P < 0.0001$). When tested within a clean arena,
317 there was a general lower interest of both control (mean \pm SE, residence time: $21.20 \text{ s} \pm 3.44$;
318 visits: 1.08 ± 0.04) and neonicotinoid-exposed (residence time: $30.72 \text{ s} \pm 6.65$; visits: $1.25 \pm$
319 0.07) parasitoids, compared to all the other treatments when collectively considered (residence
320 time, control group: $t = 10.548$, $df = 309$, $P < 0.0001$; residence time, neonicotinoid: $t = 9.987$, df
321 $= 298$, $P < 0.0001$; visits, control group: $z = 5.755$, $P < 0.0001$; visits, neonicotinoid: $z = 5.004$,
322 $P < 0.0001$).

323

324 *3.2. Experiment 2. Confirmation of Trissolcus japonicus associative learning behaviour on H.*
325 *halys and evaluation of memory retention (open arena bioassays)*

326 Conditioned parasitoids in the control group exhibited a gradual increase in their residence time
327 when tested at different times following conditioning, while the number of visits did not change
328 (Table 1). On the contrary, neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids did not exhibit any gradual change
329 in residence time, but a reduction in the number of visits (Table 1).

330 Furthermore, parasitoids with oviposition experience acquired in the absence of host traces
331 exhibited a higher residence time and number of visits when successively exposed to host-
332 contaminated area, compared to parasitoids with oviposition experience conducted in presence of
333 host traces (Table 1).

334

335 3.3. Experiment 3. Influence of the combined effect of neonicotinoid exposition and presence of

336 *H. halys* traces on the locomotory activity (kinetic) of naïve *T. japonicus* (closed arena

337 bioassays)

338 Combinations of neonicotinoid and *H. halys* traces differently influenced the linear speed ($F_{2,57}$:

339 19.37, $P < 0.0001$), tortuosity ($F_{2,57}$: 16.99, $P < 0.0001$), and activity ($F_{3,56}$: 35.78, $P < 0.0001$) of

340 parasitoids walking on the arena (Figure 2, Table S6). More specifically, naïve female parasitoids

341 exposed to host traces reduced their linear speed ($F_{1,57}$: 25.47, $P < 0.0001$) and increased the

342 tortuosity of their trajectory ($F_{1,57}$: 17.25, $P = 0.0001$) compared to females in a clean arena.

343 When females were exposed to neonicotinoid, they increased their linear speed ($F_{1,57}$: 13.25, $P =$

344 0.0006), and reduced the tortuosity of their movement ($F_{1,57}$: 16.73, $P = 0.0001$), compared to

345 females exposed to acetone. Neonicotinoid also reduced the overall activity of the females ($F_{1,56}$:

346 84.00, $P < 0.0001$), with a stronger effect in presence of traces of *H. halys* ($F_{2,57}$: 9.63, $P =$

347 0.003).

348

349 4. Discussion

350 In this study, we present original findings on the close-range foraging behaviour of naïve and

351 conditioned females of the egg parasitoid *T. japonicus*, either exposed or not to a low

352 concentration of a neonicotinoid insecticide. We confirmed our hypothesis that chemical traces

353 originating from females of *H. halys* and *A. custos* induce arrestment response in the parasitoid *T.*

354 *japonicus* (experiment 1), representing thus a reliable signal of the host presence ([Conti and](#)

355 [Colazza, 2012](#); [Bertoldi et al., 2021](#); [Greenberg et al., 2023](#)). Then, we found that parasitoid

356 conditioning reduced the foraging behaviour (experiment 1). This is likely due to associative

357 learning, as in absence of continuous experience the parasitoid gradually returned to its original

358 foraging behaviour (experiment 2). Additionally, exposition to low neonicotinoid concentration
359 induced an increase in the time spent in the area contaminated with stink bug traces,
360 independently from other factors considered (experiment 1). Notably, the observed change was
361 associated with an alteration of the kinetics of the parasitoid walking behaviour (experiment 3).
362 Lastly, we highlighted that although the neonicotinoid did not appear to alter the associative
363 learning ability of the parasitoid (after 1 h), it affected its memory retention, as the learned
364 behaviour remained unchanged for about three days, whereas it gradually disappeared over time
365 in the control parasitoids (experiment 2).

366 Data on residence time and number of visits of *T. japonicus* confirmed that the parasitoid can
367 detect the traces left by physogastric females of *H. halys*, eventually exhibiting arrestment
368 response ([Boyle et al., 2020a](#); [Malek et al., 2021](#)) and showed for the first time that *T. japonicus*
369 also responds to traces of *A. custos* (experiment 1). For *T. japonicus* on *H. halys*, this response
370 was also confirmed by the low linear speed and high tortuosity walking behaviour (experiment 3)
371 ([Boyle et al., 2020a](#)). In addition, the higher preference of *T. japonicus* for *H. halys* rather than *A.*
372 *custos* reflects the high suitability of the parasitoid for its primary, highly suitable host, compared
373 to the less suitable host ([Sabbatini-Peverieri et al., 2021](#); [Chierici et al., 2023](#)). Similarly,
374 previous studies revealed that *T. japonicus* spent more time on plant leaves contaminated by
375 kairomones from *H. halys* rather than from *Podisus maculiventris* (Say) (Hemiptera:
376 Pentatomidae) ([Boyle et al., 2020b](#)). Because of the preference of the parasitoid for *H. halys* and
377 the existence of ecological filters limiting exploitation of *A. custos* by *T. japonicus* ([Chierici et](#)
378 [al., 2023](#)), we can speculate that oviposition on this latter host would be absent or somewhat
379 limited in natural fields ([Moraglio et al., 2020](#); [Moraglio et al., 2021](#); [Falagiarda et al., 2023](#);
380 [Haye et al., 2023](#)).

381 The reduced foraging behaviour of conditioned *T. japonicus* in the presence of host traces would
382 suggest an improved ability of the parasitoid to quickly assess a similar habitat for the possible
383 presence of egg masses. This process eventually resulted in a fast patch-leaving decision and can
384 be ascribed to associative learning ([Waage, 1978](#); [Papaj and Prokopy, 1989](#); [Vet et al., 1995](#)). We
385 can hypothesise that chemical cues from stink bug traces, possibly in combination with visual
386 cues from the arena, experienced first during oviposition and later during the subsequent visit,
387 appeared to be fundamental in promoting behavioural changes. In this sense, the parasitoid may
388 benefit from the acquired experience and does not waste extra time in areas where the probability
389 to find host eggs is low ([van Giessen et al., 1993](#)). Likewise, in wind tunnel, the parasitoid
390 *Microplitis croceipes* Cresson (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) learned to associate a rewarding
391 experience (oviposition on host), with a physical environment, and when the parasitoid was
392 subsequently re-introduced in the same area (without host) it exhibited a faster explorative
393 behaviour, demonstrated by a reduced re-visit of the area ([van Giessen et al., 1993](#)).

394 With regard to the parasitoid conditioning protocol we used, which involved a single associative
395 trial between oviposition experience and host traces, we found that previous studies had
396 produced variable results. Generalist and specialist parasitoids differ in the number of events
397 needed to form an associative learning ([Hoedjes et al., 2011](#); [Giunti et al., 2015](#); [Adam et al.,](#)
398 [2022](#)). One explanation of this is that because generalists forage in more unpredictable
399 environments than specialists, they need to be able to adapt quickly to changing conditions, and a
400 propensity for associative learning may be a necessary skill ([Geervliet et al., 1998](#); [Segura et al.,](#)
401 [2007](#)). On the contrary, a specialist parasitoid is expected to gradually adjust its behaviour only if
402 the conditioning stimulus is repeatedly provided ([Hoedjes et al., 2011](#)). The generalist *Cotesia*
403 *glomerata* L. formed long-term memory after a single conditioning trial, whereas the closely
404 related specialist parasitoid *C. rubecula* (Marshall) (both Hymenoptera: Braconidae) required

405 multiple conditioning trials ([Smid et al., 2007](#)). Similar results were obtained with the closely
406 related parasitic wasp of the genus *Nasonia* ([Hoedjes and Smid, 2014](#)). The generalist *N.*
407 *vitripennis* (Walker) demonstrated associative learning capability after one single conditioning
408 trial, whereas the specialist *N. giraulti* (Darling) (both Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) necessitated
409 of at least two consecutive trials ([Hoedjes and Smid, 2014](#)). *Trissolcus japonicus* is polyphagous
410 within Scelionidae ([Haye et al., 2020](#); [Sabbatini-Peverieri et al., 2021](#)), and this would explain
411 the observed different behaviour just after one conditioning trial. However, different results were
412 found in the literature of Scelionidae. For example, the residence time of female *Trissolcus*
413 *basalis* (Wollaston) (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae) in an area contaminated with stink bug traces of
414 either *Nezara viridula* L. (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) or *H. halys* was not altered by its status,
415 either naïve or conditioned (rewarding oviposition experience in presence of host traces) ([Peri et](#)
416 [al., 2006](#); [Peri et al., 2021](#)). Therefore, additional investigations are needed to understand the
417 possible effect of other biotic and abiotic factors on parasitoid conditioning.

418 When *T. japonicus* was exposed to low neonicotinoid concentration, it exhibited a prolonged
419 residence time compared to parasitoids of the control group (experiment 1). Contact with host
420 kairomones induces a stimulation of the central nervous system ([Marion-Poll, 2020](#)). Because
421 neonicotinoids act as agonists of nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, exposure to such
422 molecules can increase stimulation ([Bicker and Kreissl, 1994](#); [Yamada et al., 1999](#); [Bohbot and](#)
423 [Pitts, 2015](#)), ultimately leading to a deficit in chemical orientation ([Dupuis et al., 2012](#); [Andrione](#)
424 [et al., 2016](#)) and this might explain an increased residence time of the parasitoid in areas
425 contaminated by host kairomones ([Delpuech et al., 2005](#)). In our case, the increased *T. japonicus*
426 residence time could be interpreted either as a consequence of intense stimulation of the central
427 nervous system, or as a consequence of impaired walking behaviour, as demonstrated by the
428 higher number of arrestment events (lower activity index). Similar sublethal effects of different

429 insecticides were observed in other parasitoid species. In experimental arena, females of
430 *Leptopilina heterotoma* Thomson (Hymenoptera: Figitidae) previously exposed for 24 h to
431 chlorpyrifos or deltamethrin doses causing 20% of mortality exhibited higher residence time in
432 the area contaminated with host kairomones compared to control area ([Delpuech et al., 2005](#)).
433 Low doses of cyfluthrin increased the residence time of the parasitoid *Telenomus busseolae*
434 Gahan (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae) in the area contaminated by scales of the host *Sesamia*
435 *nonagrioides* Lefebvre (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) ([Bayram et al., 2010](#)). Treatment with
436 imidacloprid LC₁₀ and LC₅₀ altered the host-seeking ability of the parasitoid *Leptopilina*
437 *drosophilae* (Kieffer) (Hymenoptera: Figitidae), eventually resulting in a reduced parasitisation
438 efficacy ([Shi et al., 2024](#)). A similar neonicotinoid exposition induced in *Nasonia vitripennis*
439 (Walker) (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) and *Aphidius gifuensis* Ashmead (Hymenoptera:
440 Aphidiidae) a lack of preference for host-related odours ([Tappert et al., 2017](#); [Kang et al., 2018](#)).
441 In terms of locomotion, we found that although neonicotinoid-exposed *T. japonicus* females
442 could still detect host traces, walking behaviour was also characterised by a change in linear
443 speed and tortuosity, compared to females of the control group (experiment 3). Insecticide effects
444 on locomotion were also observed in other parasitoids and in predators. Acetamiprid injected in
445 the American cockroach determined rapid coordinated movements followed by uncoordinated
446 movements ([Tan et al., 2007](#)). Compared to control, low doses of cyfluthrin and deltamethrin
447 increased the linear speed of *T. busseolae* in areas containing host kairomones ([Bayram et al.,](#)
448 [2010](#)). Sublethal concentration of acetamiprid caused a deficiency in the locomotion ability of
449 *Coccinella septempunctata* L. and *Harmonia axyridis* (Pallas) (both Coleoptera: Coccinellidae),
450 eventually resulting in decreased predatory efficiency ([You et al., 2022](#)).
451 Intriguingly, neonicotinoid application did not change the parasitoid learning ability evaluated
452 after 1 h from the occurrence of the conditioning regardless of the host species (experiment 1).

453 This result agrees with findings from previous studies of sublethal effects of neonicotinoids on
454 learning behaviour in Hymenoptera ([Williamson et al., 2013](#); [Piironen et al., 2016](#); [Lämsä et al.,
455 2018](#)). In bumblebees, a low dose of imidacloprid did not induce a reduction in the association of
456 flower colours with a rewarding experience even if a decreased foraging motivation was
457 observed ([Lämsä et al., 2018](#)). Similarly, honey bees exposed to contact with acetamiprid (range
458 of doses between 1:10 and 1:100 of LD50) did not alter their learning ability ([El Hassani et al.,
459 2008](#)).

460 Notably, neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids exhibited an extended memory retention, as the
461 residence time towards host traces of *H. halys* did not sensibly change within 72 h following
462 conditioning (experiment 2). Although further confirmation would be needed, our results are in
463 agreement with some previous studies. For example, through activation of nicotinic
464 acetylcholine receptors in the mushroom bodies and antennal lobes, the neonicotinoid
465 imidacloprid enhanced long term memory in *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae)
466 ([Williamson et al., 2013](#)).

467 Although the use of *T. japonicus* for biological control of *H. halys* could allow significant
468 reduction of pest populations, egg parasitoids alone might not be successful enough to reduce
469 field infestations by stink bugs at an acceptable level ([Abram et al., 2020](#)). Thus, the concurrent
470 use of synthetic insecticides might still be necessary in the field, for instance to knock-down the
471 invasive pest when its density is simply too high to be controlled by natural enemies. To our
472 knowledge, this study is the first to investigate the effect of an insecticide on the associative
473 learning of an egg parasitoid, and some aspects should be considered in future investigations.
474 Further research should be conducted to evaluate also lower concentrations of the neonicotinoid
475 acetamiprid and alternative modes of contamination of *T. japonicus*. Exposure to dry insecticide
476 residues is a common procedure ([Ricupero et al., 2020](#)), and is likely to occur when the

477 parasitoid moves from field edges or semi-natural habitats into an orchard in search of host eggs
478 following aerial pesticide application ([Lowenstein et al., 2019](#)). However, it is also possible that
479 the parasitoid is contaminated by topical contact with liquid droplets during (e.g., pesticide drift)
480 or immediately after spraying, or by oral ingestion.

481 In addition, similar to other studies ([Peri et al., 2006](#); [Bertoldi et al., 2021](#)), our experimental
482 arena consisted of a sheet of filter paper. Considering that parasitoids mostly feed on plant
483 leaves, additional setups can be evaluated considering different substrates. Previous studies have
484 elucidated the effect of leaf characteristics and plant structure on the walking behaviour of
485 natural enemies ([Romeis et al., 2005](#); [Rostás et al., 2008](#)) or the effect of the plant cuticle in the
486 adsorption of pesticides and host traces ([Colazza et al., 2009](#); [Buchholz and Trapp, 2016](#)).

487 From the parasitoid side, possible fitness costs ([Dukas and Duan, 2000](#)), effect of memory
488 reinforcement ([Smid and Vet, 2016](#)), and changes in parasitoid-host functional response ([Wang
489 et al., 2019](#)) are behavioural and physiological traits that may vary with learning status and
490 insecticide exposition. Their evaluation may be useful for a better understanding of the factors
491 that promote or limit the compatibility of classical biological control strategies with the use of
492 chemical pesticides against invasive herbivore species.

493

494 **CRedit authorship contribution statement:**

495 Gabriele Rondoni: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data
496 curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

497 Elena Chierici: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation,
498 Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

499 Elissa Daher: Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

500 Franco Famiani: Writing – review & editing.

501 Jacques Brodeur: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

502 Eric Conti: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding
503 acquisition.

504

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506 Virtual Special Issue “Recent advances in characterizing trophic connections in biological
507 control”. Eric Conti is Editorial Board Member of Biological Control. The other Authors declare
508 no conflict of interest.

509

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512

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518

519 **Figure legends**

520 Figure 1: Residence time (A) and number of visits (B) of *Trissolcus japonicus* females evaluated
521 in Experiment 1 under combined effect of insecticide exposition (control or neonicotinoid),
522 parasitoid conditioning (naïve or conditioned), and host species traces (*Halyomorpha halys*,
523 “Hh”, or *Arma custos*, “Ac”). Responses were evaluated using linear model (residence time) and
524 quasi-Poisson generalised linear model (number of visits) (Tables S4, and S5). Three- and two-
525 way interactions among insecticide treatment, parasitoid conditioning, and host species traces
526 were not significant (Tables S2, and S3). Neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids exhibited higher
527 residence time compared to control. Conditioned parasitoids exhibited lower residence time and
528 frequency of visits compared to naïve parasitoids. Traces of *H. halys* induced in parasitoids
529 higher residence time and number of visits compared to traces of *A. custos*.

530

531 Figure 2: Linear speed, tortuosity, and activity of naïve *Trissolcus japonicus* females evaluated in
532 Experiment 3 under combined effect of *Halyomorpha halys* (“Hh”) traces and insecticide
533 (neonicotinoid). Responses were evaluated using linear models (Table S6, and S7). The presence
534 of *H. halys* traces in the arena induced a parasitoid arrestment behaviour, demonstrated by lower
535 linear speed and higher tortuosity, if compared to a clean arena. The presence of host traces also
536 reduced the activity of the parasitoid females (i.e., the time fraction they were actively moving),
537 but only for neonicotinoid parasitoids. If compared to control (acetone only, grey bars),
538 exposition to neonicotinoid (black bars) induced higher linear speed, lower tortuosity, and lower
539 activity.

540

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880 Figure 1. Residence time (A) and number of visits (B) of *Trissolcus japonicus* females evaluated
 881 in Experiment 1 under combined effect of insecticide exposition (control or neonicotinoid),
 882 parasitoid conditioning (naïve or conditioned), and host species traces (*Halyomorpha halys*,
 883 “Hh”, or *Arma custos*, “Ac”). Responses were evaluated using linear model (residence time) and
 884 quasi-Poisson generalised linear model (number of visits) (Tables S4, and S5). Three- and two-
 885 way interactions among insecticide treatment, parasitoid conditioning, and host species traces
 886 were not significant (Tables S2, and S3). Neonicotinoid-exposed parasitoids exhibited higher
 887 residence time compared to control. Conditioned parasitoids exhibited lower residence time and
 888 frequency of visits compared to naïve parasitoids. Traces of *H. halys* induced in parasitoids
 889 higher residence time and number of visits compared to traces of *A. custos*.

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892 Figure 2. Linear speed, tortuosity, and activity of naïve *Trissolcus japonicus* females evaluated in
893 Experiment 3 under combined effect of *Halyomorpha halys* (“Hh”) traces and insecticide
894 (neonicotinoid). Responses were evaluated using linear models (Tables S6, and S7). The
895 presence of *H. halys* traces in the arena induced a parasitoid arrestment behaviour, demonstrated
896 by lower linear speed and higher tortuosity, if compared to a clean arena. The presence of host
897 traces also reduced the activity of the parasitoid females (i.e., the time fraction they were actively
898 moving), but only for neonicotinoid parasitoids. If compared to control (acetone only, grey bars),
899 exposition to neonicotinoid (black bars) induced higher linear speed, lower tortuosity, and lower
900 activity.

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916 Table 1: Coefficients and significance level for each explanatory variable retained for evaluating *Trissolcus japonicus* associative

917 learning.

Parasitoid group	Explanatory variable	Residence time (linear model)				Visits (quasi-Poisson GLM)			
		Estimate	SE	t	P	Estimate	SE	z	P
Parasitoids in control group, tested at 1 h (treatment 1c), 24 h (treatment 2a), and 72 h (treatment 2b) since conditioning	Intercept	4.38	0.28	15.50	< 0.0001	1.06	0.17	6.24	< 0.0001
	Time	0.55	0.13	4.24	< 0.0001	0.01	0.08	0.14	0.89
Parasitoids exposed to the neonicotinoid, tested at 1 h (treatment 1d), 24 h (treatment 2c), or 72 h (treatment 2d) since conditioning	Intercept	3.17	0.12	27.05	< 0.0001	1.46	0.19	7.57	< 0.0001
	Time	-0.09	0.05	-1.61	0.11	-0.38	0.10	-3.84	0.0002
Conditioned parasitoids, with oviposition experience conducted in presence (treatment 1c) or absence (treatment 2e) of host traces	Intercept	6.17	0.28	22.17	< 0.0001	1.15	0.10	11.43	< 0.0001
	Traces (absent vs. present)	3.10	0.39	7.96	< 0.0001	0.57	0.12	4.60	< 0.0001

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